

WAYS TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ACTIVITY OF THE KOKAN STATE PEDAGOGICAL INSTITUTE BASED ON THE 3.0 MODEL IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. *This article based on the 3.0 model in higher education, there is an opinion about ways to improve the effectiveness of the Kokand State Pedagogical Institute.*

Keywords: *time management, independent education, additional literature, textbook, lesson, new education.*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a promising model of the development of the national economy, the "knowledge economy" or "intellectual economy" model, the issues of rapid development of industry and other sectors of the national economy by increasing the role and contribution of science in the innovative development of the country are reflected in the article.

Currently, in many industrialized and developing countries of the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "knowledge economy" or "intellectual economy" model is being adopted as a promising model of national economy development. By increasing the role and contribution of science in the innovative development of the country, long-term projects of rapid development of industry and other sectors of the national economy are being developed. In this regard, there are a number of emerging global trends related to the increasing importance of intellectual property created and commercialized by HEIs. World practice shows that, as universities are open and rapidly developing platforms, regional and global economies of states becoming a platform that provides its advantage, it is able to cope with the task of a complex integrator of developments and technologies that require science in the best way. The interaction of activities with the necessary resource base to provide a constant flow of active youth has the ability to form multidisciplinary research projects aimed at solving a single complex problem. Also, the economy and society are changing

has the necessary potential to create specialists in new knowledge and professions that meet the requirements. This is also confirmed by the annual income from licensing and innovation activities of many international companies established in the world's leading universities. This important development was made possible by the transition of many leading foreign universities to the "University 3.0" or "entrepreneurial university" development model. The activator of this process, in particular, in the United States, was the Bayh-Dole Act, adopted in 1980, which established the legal basis for the free transfer of intellectual property to its creators - developers and scientific institutions and started the process. It has created many university companies for large-scale patenting of research results and commercialization of scientific developments. Currently, there are three main models of university development.

"University 1.0" is an educational institution that prepares specialists for professional activity in some sectors of the economy and social sphere. In the traditional and classic "University 1.0" model, only education was a priority. The teacher gives a lecture, the student writes a summary. "University 1.0", i.e. "first-generation university" is only an educational space, the

purpose of which is to deliver knowledge. Educational institutions that perform the function of education and training of specialists for economic sectors and social sphere only.

"University 2.0" are educational institutions in which research and research work play an important role. The main task - a new function for education - is to conduct scientific research for the industrial sector. Universities play a leading role in the implementation of scientific research and innovative development in addition to the educational process. "University 2.0"? The "second generation university" model is considered to be a school specializing in scientific research in addition to education. Educational institutions developed since the 19th century are called "research universities". "University 2.0" creates new knowledge through scientific research activities; will be a center of consulting services for market participants; conducts scientific research on orders from the industry, lays the foundation for new technologies.

"University 3.0" is a scientific, production and educational center that integrates educational and research activities with the commercialization of scientists' developments at its base. The main goal of the "University 3.0" model is to create an integrated educational, research and entrepreneurship environment in universities by applying the model of a flexible modern company, start-up incubator, regional development centers with a priority on leadership development. competencies as a provider. However, the "University 3.0" development model should not only be related to the concept of "commercialization of scientific research results", because in its meaning it implies the implementation of a wider authority - the ability to manage the results of intellectual activity. By creating an entrepreneurial environment within the innovation ecosystem, it is aimed at the modernization of innovative renewal (development of small innovative activities) and the development of new markets and the introduction of new technologies, as well as creating a unique academic environment of the institute. This project is a systematic prerequisite for the intellectual modernization of traditional industries. It involves creating conditions and choosing growth points for the knowledge-intensive economy of Uzbekistan, then forming competencies in the target segments of the intellectual economy and raising them to leading positions in the world. , future leading universities, entrepreneurial universities will be impossible without the implementation of the "Development Concept" or the "University 3.0" model. At the same time, it is impossible to implement the "University 3.0" concept without modernizing higher education in the context of the development of the knowledge economy, which involves the improvement of the efficiency of higher education through innovations and the achievement of new modern quality.

The need to implement the "University 3.0" concept is confirmed by the experience of European universities trying to restructure and integrate into the modern economy in order to adapt to the knowledge economy and entrepreneurial society. It envisages making changes and additions aimed at systematically and interdependently studying the issues of creating a business environment. Also, in order to increase the efficiency of scientific research and innovative activity, to ensure the commercialization of the results of intellectual activity, the concept includes innovative infrastructure subjects (scientific-technological parks, technology transfer centers), the creation and development of business incubators is envisaged. The policy and development strategy of universities on the formation of an entrepreneurial environment It includes comprehensive measures to create various incentives to engage in entrepreneurial activities based on the formation of students', teachers' and researchers' perceptions that entrepreneurship is the only factor. First of all, the development of the university as an "area of advanced development" is the task of "creating future professions", realizing the potential of department branches and

educational, scientific and industrial clusters, as well as educational systems: engineering, technical, it is solved by directing activities aimed at economic and other development.

Secondly, the university should improve the system of training highly qualified scientific personnel in the field of innovation and ensure the independent formation of future competence, which will be solved by establishing relations with advanced world experience, cooperation with leaders and participation in their projects. transformation, including the system of university startups, student entrepreneurship, improvement of the educational process (business competencies), attracting qualified teachers and representatives of the business environment, developing business plans, forming the skills and qualifications of entrepreneurs who have started work. Financial support for entrepreneurial initiatives of young people Creation of university-based crowdfunding platforms to attract funds from interested parties for support is one of the perspectives that should be further developed. "University 3.0" k implementation of the concept aims to achieve two main results by the university: training of a new category of specialists - technology entrepreneurs and creation of potential business by the entrepreneurial university. The progressive movement in the implementation of the University 3.0 development model by HEIs is carried out by creating a flexible system of training and retraining of scientific personnel, as well as by closely integrating professional education, university science and production, realizing the country's potential. Historically, the role of the university has changed depending on economic and social conditions, they have acquired new functions, which are reflected in the characteristics of these models. The concept of "University 3.0" was developed by Burton R. Clark in 1998, who also introduced the term "Entrepreneurial universities" into scientific circulation (the term "University 3.0" is more often used in Russian-language literature). However, a clear definition of this concept has not yet been developed.

According to most researchers, University 3.0 is a higher education institution capable of attracting additional financial resources to support its activities, a university that uses innovative methods of teaching, that establishes close cooperation with the business community, carries out developments is the university to go to. university researchers are being introduced. The concept of "University 3.0" (including "entrepreneurial university") is popular abroad and has been shaping the development trends of world higher education in recent decades. Universities, by definition, impart knowledge sources of formation are also the place of formation of human capital. Accordingly, they are the most obvious link between the most innovative, high-tech and rapidly developing new sectors of the economy and young people who have not yet fully entered the labor market and can be formed by developing their skills and qualifications. It is logical to look at it as in. This connection allows to optimize funds for the development of science and innovation, as well as to significantly increase the competitiveness and attractiveness of universities. Among the main difficulties in the implementation of the "University 3.0" concept in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that the weak connection between the labor market and higher education, the flexibility of the educational process and its content is still relatively low.

Based on the decision of the President of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the "University 3.0" model, which is planned to be gradually introduced in our country, is based on education, science, innovation and is a model for research commercialization. This was announced at the press conference held at the Information and Mass Communications Agency with the participation of representatives of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education. they will have the opportunity to sell the scientific research products they have produced. For example,

universities can open a special technology park, conduct scientific research and commercialize their developments. Then it will be possible not only to impart knowledge to the graduates, but also to apply the acquired knowledge to life. "The Ministry of Higher Education has been implementing the project "Science 20-20" since March 2018. Within the framework of the project, it is planned to provide teachers with scientific information and improve the skills of employees in writing scientific articles. Unfortunately, there is not a single Uzbek journal among the 23,500 most reliable (scientific) journals, so it is planned to include the scientific journals of our country in the Scopus database. This also increases the prestige of higher educational institutions," said Ismailov. This concept also includes the establishment of the National Council for Higher Education in the form of non-profit, non-governmental organizations, whose main tasks are to improve the quality of higher education by studying the opinions of the public and employers. "Implementation of the University 3.0 model will lead to the formation of a new university structure, to retain young people in university science, to increase the competitiveness of higher education in the global educational space, and to provide opportunities for regional higher education institutions," explains Igor Karpenko.

According to him, it is intended to implement the experimental project on the practical testing of the university of the new format "University 3.0", which envisages the creation of an integrated educational, scientific and entrepreneurial environment within universities for the commercialization of scientific developments. Today, the conditions have already been created for universities to switch to this model in the implementation of the tasks of directing specialists to practice, improving the quality and efficiency of training. In the developed countries of the world, the "University 4.0" model is being formed, which in some cases is beyond the power of corporate or academic science. allows solving the most complex tasks, but this can be achieved only after it has been developed. Only the successful implementation of the "University 3.0" model, which is based on the unique equipment, highly qualified personnel and, most importantly, the concentration of the creativity of young people in higher educational institutions, can bring education to a higher level," said Minister A. Tashkulov. In the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the issue of gradually introducing the concept of "University 3.0" into our lives is emphasized. is also engaged in the commercialization of the results of scientific research. Entrepreneurial culture is developed in "University 3.0" and effective communication with representatives of business circles is established. In such a university, technological start-ups are created and patents are regularly registered. A clear example of this is Silicon Valley, California. According to research, only 0.3 of the total number of universities in the world percent is recognized as compatible with the "University 3.0" model. Universities of our country are faced with the issue of commercialization of research results by 2030. In this case, it will be possible for our universities to occupy high places in the ratings of internationally recognized organizations. Step-by-step transition to new-generation universities provides an opportunity to integrate into global educational processes. Traditional universities are unable to meet the requirements of the times. Education is important, but not enough. Theoretical studies are important, but if they are disconnected from reality, they remain theoretical. Today's generation of universities should learn to commercialize the results of scientific research. This will increase their prestige and credibility both locally and internationally. Only flexible universities can compete.

Based on the University 3.0 model, several works are being carried out to organize the activities of the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute. In recent years, the publication of the National

rating of higher education institutions in our republic has also created the basis for the further development of this healthy competitive environment. In order to assess the level of competitiveness of the higher education institution, the quality of educational services provided to students, teachers and students of each Higher Education Institution participate in various contests, Olympiads, and other national and international level competitions and events. In recent years, the publication of the National rating of higher education institutions in our republic has also created the basis for the further development of this healthy competitive environment. Despite the fact that the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute provides sufficient results in all areas, the position of our institute in the national rating is low. We will conduct a SWOT analysis based on the results of QDPI's activities in various directions as a HEI and determine the strengths and weaknesses of the institution, as well as potential opportunities and threats. (Table-1)

Table 1 – QDPI SWOT-analysis

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Availability of highly qualified teaching staff and specialists from the industry according to the profiles of the taught subjects;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • regular training of personnel in enterprises equipped with modern equipment; • Ensuring the creation of incentives, involvement and reward mechanisms for employees for the activities carried out to improve the quality of educational services; • Positive image of QDPI; • Fulfilling the specified indicators of the admission quota; • Demand for the proposed educational courses; • Participation of employers in the final and intermediate attestation of graduates in all specialties; • effective cooperation with city and regional employers; • To cooperate with other educational organizations in the city of Ko'kan and surrounding districts, similar and supporting higher education institutions of the republic; • Active and purposeful work of career orientation (Open days, advertising brochures, posting of information on the site, participation in job fairs of educational places, career orientation meetings with graduates of Kokan and surrounding schools); • Use of distance learning elements; 	<p>Insufficient classrooms (lessons are held in two shifts);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of qualified and potential teachers in the main state in specialized subjects; • The scientific potential is much lower than the required level; • The average age of teachers with scientific potential is over 48 years. • Absence of a modern, constantly updated material base of laboratories and computer equipment • lack of long-term social cooperation with enterprises and organizations to train highly qualified specialists

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness of KokanDPI's successes and plans through mass media (television, radio, institute website, social networks); • 	
opportunities	threats
<p>expansion of international relations, participation of students and teachers in international educational projects;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of new educational information technologies in the educational process • expanding the list of educational programs; • development of research and innovative activities; • Ensuring the permanent composition of teachers of specialized subjects; • a systematic approach to the assessment of the quality of the educational process; • broadcast of advanced management experience and pedagogical achievements; • development of educational marketing; • long-term social cooperation with enterprises and organizations for the training of highly qualified specialists; • 	<p>the rate of growth of the need for highly educated specialists in the region is not high enough;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lack of permanent demand by employers for the knowledge and skills of graduates; • decrease in the level of knowledge of graduates of general educational institutions; • Low interest of students in extracurricular activities • Reducing the number of students studying in the budget.

In fact, the number "3" is a new concept and prepares specialists for professional activity in some sectors of the economy and social spheres. Along with the acceleration of knowledge growth in the labor market in high-tech industries, processes of uncertain social significance are taking place. Along with robotization, which is leading to the disappearance of many professions and the reduction of jobs, ageism is becoming a serious problem for high-tech industries, especially the IT sector. All this makes the problem of ensuring the competitiveness of the higher education institutions of our country, preventing the "brain drain", as well as strengthening the contribution of higher education to the development of the country's economy, urgent. The first steps towards a modern university are universities, state and business was to expand the so-called "university component" in the preparation of curricula and standards, which would help to qualitatively revise the mutual cooperation in the field of education, to expand the independence of educational programs and educational institutions. Despite the objectively late start of the "University 3.0" project, state and non-state organizations are well aware of its importance in the development of the country's economy and human capital. The inclusion of technical universities in the project is an important achievement.

REFERENCES

1. O'zb.R.ning "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi qonuni. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni, 23.09.2020 y O'RQ-637-son
2. Farberman BL. "Ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar". "Fan". ToshkentL 2000y.

3. "Training Specification Standard No. (2A 58/01" 4th Edition. FAS TR EMPL AUTH- 1994. Muslimov N.A. va bosh. "Innovation ta'lim texnologiyalari"
4. Yevropa oliy ta'lim hududi. Yevropa ta'lim vazirlarining qo'shma bayonoti. G. Bolonya, 1999 yil 19 iyun. Ishtirokchi davlatlar vazirlarning Berlin deklaratsiyasi Boloniya jarayoni. 2003 yil 19 sentyabr.
5. Djurinskiy A.N. Zamonaviy dunyoda ta'limning rivojlanishi. NI.: "Akademiya" nashriyot markazi, 2006.
6. Plaksiy S.I. Oliy ta'limning sifat ko'rsatkichlari [Elektron resurs] // Bilim Tushunish. Malaka. Axborot-gumanitar portal. 2004. URL: [http: // www. zpujournal.ru/](http://www.zpujournal.ru/) (kirişh sanasi: 21.02.2011).
7. Alferov Yu.S. Dunyoda ta'limning rivojlanishini monitoring qilish // Pedagogika. 2008. N! 7. S. 73-84.